

Latvian and Chinese art: contact points in the historical and contemporary context

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The goal of this work is to find and examine all the possible contact points of Latvian and Chinese art at any historical phase, i. e.:

- to identify periods, ways and reasons for the appearance of Chinese works or objects of art in the Latvian territory;
- to mention historical and contemporary Chinese and Latvian personalities directly related to this interaction and the promotion of the Chinese culture in Latvia;
- to find and describe specific Chinese or Latvian works or objects of art that prove the existence of such contact points;
- to acknowledge Chinese art exhibitions, public lectures, and various events in terms of their impact on the Latvian viewer's perception of China.

Relevance

Since the last centuries BC, two routes connected China with European countries: a land route and a sea route. Latvia and China are geographically very far apart, and the interaction between the two was historically less close than, for instance, between China and such countries as Britain, France, Italy, the Netherlands, Portugal, several other European countries and Russia. Latvian territory was also affected by the trends of Orientalism¹, though to a lesser extent. Although the ancient version of the Silk Road passed significantly southwards of the eastern coast of the Baltic Sea, Chinese goods could still reach the territory of what is now Latvia either overland, with the help of rivers, or directly from large European ports².

¹ Orientalism is the imitation or depiction of aspects in the Eastern world. Edward W. Saïd. *Orientalism*. 1978.

² Li Qingxin. *Maritime silk road*. 2009

The Silk and Spice Routes. Map³.

Over the past decades, it can be noted that Latvia is becoming increasingly open to China, and China, in turn, is also very interested in cooperation with this small country. The friendship between China and Latvia partly stems from the fact that China was among the first to recognize Latvia's independence in 1991⁴. The two countries are also connected by town twinning: for instance, Riga is twinned with Suzhou (since 1997), Taipei (since 2001) and Beijing (since 2004), Daugavpils is twinned with Harbin (since 2003). Such connections enable the development of economic, tourist and cultural exchanges⁵.

Since the turn of the 21st century, the Chinese Embassy has become increasingly interested in organizing cultural events in Latvia. The Confucius Institute and the Asian department of the Latvian National Library have also been very active. Chinese cultural centres opened their doors in Riga and Cesis; Flying Brush, a Chinese painting society, was established in Riga, as well as the Latvian-Chinese Educational Association. Regular events in Riga include Chinese culture festivals, private and public exhibitions of Chinese art, public lectures by professors of the Oriental Department of the University of Latvia and Academy of Culture, by art historians of the Latvian National Museum of Art and the Riga Bourse Art Museum, and scholarly conferences on Chinese culture. Another important link between two countries is provided by major Chinese artists who come to Latvia for long-term or short-term visits and are very active during their stay; finally, by increasingly open and active interaction and communication of Latvians and Chinese through the Internet.

In July 2017, the Latvian Institute of International Relations launched the New Silk Road programme, with the main objectives to promote and to coordinate research activities involving

³ https://en.unesco.org/silkroad/sites/silkroad/files/SilkRoadMapOKS_big.jpg

⁴ Latvijas Vēstnesis. ĀM Informācijas un sabiedrisko attiecību departaments. Ārlietu ministrs, tiekoties ar Ķīnas Valsts padomes Informācijas biroja viceministru. (22.08.2006., Nr. 133) <https://www.vestnesis.lv/ta/id/142071>

⁵ Rīgas pašvaldības portāls. Rīgas Sadraudzības pilsētas.

https://pasvaldiba.riga.lv/LV/Channels/Riga_today/Riga_pasaule/sadraudzibas_pilsetas/default.htm

other 15 countries of Central and Eastern Europe and Asia⁶. Within the framework of the programme, Latvia's involvement in the exchange of transport, logistics, information, finance, digital and human capital, which is also linked to the China Belt and Road Initiative, is conceptually assessed. In this equation, the human capital also includes art.

Chinese art and chinoiserie in Europe and Russia.

The geographic location of the Latvian territory between Europe and Russia, and, at the same time, on the eastern coast of the Baltic Sea, dictates the main routes for the coming of Chinese art to Latvia and determines contact points of Latvian and Chinese art.

The silk trade with China started already in Ancient Rome. The Romans marvelled at the beauty of fabrics but knew very little about their origin. Even later, in the Middle Ages and Renaissance, rare were the travellers who managed to reach the fabulous land of China, and their stories have long been the only source of information about China in Europe. It did not help that from time to time the Chinese government decided to close their country for foreigners⁷.

Some original Chinese artworks, mostly belonging to the domain of applied art, did arrive in Europe, but their limited number could not satisfy the growing demand, which led to the emergence of the chinoiserie.

Chinoiserie (from the French *chinois* meaning 'Chinese') is the use of medieval Chinese motifs and stylistic techniques in European painting, applied art, costumes and landscape design⁸. Chinoiserie emerged in the 17th century in connection with the activities of the East India Companies and was partly based on China travel stories written by numerous travellers from Marco Polo to Matteo Ricci. Chinoiserie includes Delftware and imitations of Chinese lacquer furniture in the Netherlands. It was also present in the art of French Régence (the 1730s), Baroque and Rococo art of the mid-18th century (Austrian Rococo, Prussian or Frederician Rococo, Saxon Baroque Rocaille in Dresden, Petrine Baroque in Russia), English Neo-Classicism and Chippendale furniture and even European and Russian Art Nouveau.

Chinoiserie, initially aimed at repeating and copying Chinese works, finally turned into a style of its own, an Orientalist imitation of the Eastern art in general. Indeed, in the 17th and 18th centuries most European artisans could not tell Chinese art from Indian, Japanese or Siamese art, and, trying to achieve the feeling of exoticism, used their fantasy to build up the image of fabulously rich Oriental countries. For several reasons, it was not possible to make an exact copy of the Oriental curiosities; Europeans had therefore to invent original products based on what they saw. Since the technologies of making porcelain, lacquer, fabrics and other Chinese goods were kept secret, Europeans desperately tried to replace them with similar ones, which led to

⁶ Latvijas ārpolitikas institūts. LĀI atklāj Jaunā Zīda ceļa programmas oficiālo mājas lapu. <http://www.lai.lv/jaunumi/liia-presents-the-official-website-of-the-new-silk-road-programme-752>

⁷ «Шинуазри», или восточно-западный микс XVIII века. <https://magazeta.com/chinoiserie/>

⁸ Michael Clarke. The Concise Oxford Dictionary of Art Terms. 2010. P.56.

the emergence of new solutions. For instance, the porcelain was first brought to Europe in the 14th century; since the 16th century, Europeans tried to reproduce it and only managed to achieve their goal in the late 18th century. Before that, Europeans invented ‘their own porcelain’, faïence. Same story with lacquer and such fabrics as cotton and silk: it took centuries to learn to create similar items.

Lacking the understanding of what was depicted on prints, vases, and fabrics, and being unable to penetrate Chinese philosophy and aesthetics, European artisans filled the Chinese forms with their own ideas and created artworks according to these ideas, inventing fantastic plants and architecture, depicting people with strange bodies and faces who mostly looked like Chinese-clad Europeans, weird clothes and accessories; a Chinese observer would probably be unable to recognize anything of this as ‘his own’.

A fragment of a picture on the lacquered chest.
England. 1720 ¹⁰.

Francois Boucher. *The Chinese Garden*. 1742 ⁹.

European artisans also added new elements, foreign to Chinese aesthetics: for instance, they could frame a porcelain vessel in silver or gold. They also invented tiles with Oriental paintings, using them to cover fireplaces, stoves, decorate the interior or even entire rooms. Of course, anything of this kind is simply unthinkable in a Chinese house. The interior was also painted differently: while the Chinese used screens and partitions of light paper and silk, painting them with mineral colours or Chinese ink, Europeans painted the very walls with oil colours or covered them with panels carrying embroidery or painting on varnish. Globally, all this looked too heavy, cumbersome and over-saturated, and bold visual solutions and unimaginable patterns had

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https://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/2/23/Le_Jardin_chinois_%28detail%29_by_Fran%C3%A7ois_Boucher.jpg

¹⁰ Джекобсон Д. Китайский стиль. 2004

nothing to do with the Chinese approach. However, if chinoiserie is seen not as an attempt to imitate but as an original European style (and this is how it is perceived by the Chinese who do not identify the chinoiserie with their culture), it is quite authentic and unusual and has its *raison d'être*.

The passion for Chinese style began in Russia during the reign of Peter the Great and lasted for the entire 18th century, then faded away only to resurface in the early 20th century with the Art Nouveau. Many Chinese curiosities came to Russia through the West, but some took the route of Siberia and Russian Far Eastern cities such as Vladivostok. Russian chinoiserie was strongly influenced by French prints that used Chinese motifs, and Rococo paintings by such artists as François Boucher and Jean-Antoine Watteau. Thanks to the French prints and Enlightenment authors such as Voltaire, Confucius became popular in the 18th-century Russia as the embodiment of wise governance¹¹.

It is important to emphasize that the chinoiserie never focused on Chinese fine arts and calligraphy, only on applied arts. Indeed, there is almost no evidence of Chinese paintings or calligraphic scrolls being brought to Europe even during the peak of the chinoiserie, but even if they were brought, they stayed unnoticed for a long time. This lack of attention is believed to be caused by their incomprehensibility to the European audience in terms of aesthetics and symbols and their close connection to the Chinese language. It is known, however, that porcelain came to Europe wrapped into Chinese and Japanese prints including cheap Chinese woodblock prints *nianhua*¹². In a nutshell, until the turn of the 20th century, the Chinese culture of fine arts only reached Europe in an abridged version.

Summarizing the influence of other countries on Latvia in the historical context, we can imagine possible routes that Chinese and chinoiserie objects took to come to Latvia and the corresponding time frames. Since the Middle Ages, they would mostly be connected with German or Scandinavian influence; Polish and Dutch influence became important in the 16th and 17th centuries, starting from the 18th century, Chinese and chinoiserie objects could take a route through Russia or another European country such as France. It cannot be said that Latvia was as fascinated with chinoiserie as other European countries or Russia but the influence of Chinese art, often inseparable from that of Japan, had a significant influence on the art of Latvia in the 18th and 19th centuries and again in the early 20th century with the emergence of the Art Nouveau.

Chinese art and chinoiserie in Latvia

The analysis of Chinese and 'somewhat Chinese' objects of fine and applied art found in Europe and Latvia in particular allows to divide them into three groups: (1) objects made in China and

¹¹ Воображаемый восток: Китай «по-русски», XVIII – начало XX века (сост. О.А. Соснина), 2016.

¹² Nianhua is a form of Chinese colored woodblock print, for decoration during the Chinese New Year Holiday, then later used to depict current events. Рифтин Б. Л. Нянь-хуа. 2010.

brought to Europe or Russia, and then to Latvia; (2) objects made in Europe or Russia in an attempt to imitate the Chinese style and brought to Latvia, 3) art objects and works produced in Latvia but under a degree of Chinese influence.

The oldest Chinese object in Latvia is a ceramic cup dating from the 9th or the 10th century, discovered in 1835 during the excavation of an ancient Livonian* burial site of the 11th-12th centuries at the top of Saksu Hill (preserved in the collection of the Latvian History Museum). Most likely, this unique object is a direct witness of the old trade route that linked China with Russia. Scientists believe that the cup could follow the Great Silk Road to Central Asia, then travel along the Volga River to arrive in Volga Bulgaria and, finally, use the help of Scandinavian merchants to get to the Baltic sea coast, now in Latvia.

A cup. Stone mass, yellow-green glaze. China, the Tang Dynasty. 9th-10th century¹³.

At present, the most important collection of Oriental art in Latvia is located in the Riga Bourse Art Museum (former Latvian Museum of Foreign Art and Oriental collection of the Latvian National Museum). It features over 500 items of Chinese fine and applied arts and chinoiserie, including scrolls (16th-19th centuries), prints (18th-19th centuries), porcelain (16th-19th centuries), ceramics, weapons, fans, lacquered objects, carved furniture, statuettes, textiles, and much more¹⁴.

The second most important collection of Chinese applied art is situated in the Rundale Palace Museum in the Zemgale region of Latvia, a Baroque pearl built between 1736 and 1768 by the Italian architect Francesco Bartolomeo Rastrelli for Ernst Johann von Biron, the Duke of Courland, a favourite of Empress Anna of Russia. Rundale hosts the largest collection of porcelain in Latvia, both Chinese and European (Meissen and Delft) and many chinoiserie household items and furniture. This famous collection had a great influence on the public of the entire Baltic region¹⁵.

¹³ <http://www.lnmm.lv/lv/mmr/b/apmekle/izstades/6587-izstade-pekina-p-zida-cela-mantojums-dargumi-nacionalajiem-muzejiem>

¹⁴ Mākslas muzejs Rīgas birža (comp. Daiga Upeniece). 2011.

¹⁵ Rundāle: Rundāles pils muzejs, 2018

Chinese art objects can also be found scattered over many other Latvian museums such as the Kurzeme Provincial Museum, the Latvian History Museum, Romans Suta and Aleksandra Belcova Museum, the Art Nouveau Museum, the Fashion Museum, the Aleksandrs Čaks Museum, the Latvian National Library, the Roerich Museum, the Menzendorf House Museum, the Open Air Museum and in some other museums, as well as in private collections, antique salons and auction houses such as Vitber, Antonija, Fajans or Art Embassy, and, finally, in Chinese cultural centres, Chinese tea shops and restaurants. In 2017, during the Belt and Road Forum on International Cooperation and Exchange of Cultural Heritage, the Ethnographic Open Air Museum of Latvia received a precious Chinese cloisonné enamel vase. The vase is made by the special order for Latvian forum by Beijing master Mi Zhengxun. The idea of the vase embodies the spirit of the Silk Road – peace and cooperation, openness and exchange of knowledge¹⁶.

The Vase for an open-air museum. 2017¹⁷

Among other Chinese-influenced objects, there are shoes of a Roman Catholic Latvian bishop from the 1st quarter of the 18th century, embroidered with silk threads in the Oriental style. Many Roman Catholic priests wore such shoes; a pair of these were found in a burial in the Church of Lēnu and is now preserved in the collection of the Rundale Palace.

¹⁶ Brīvdabas muzejs saņem dāvinājuma no Ķīnas vērtīgu vāzi. 2017.

http://epadomi.lv/kulturasvestis/izstade/24082017-brivdabas_muzejs_sanem_davinajuma_no_kina

¹⁷ http://epadomi.lv/kulturasvestis/izstade/24082017-brivdabas_muzejs_sanem_davinajuma_no_kina

The pair of shoes. Kurzeme. Latvia. 18th century¹⁸.

Chinese motifs are clearly visible in Art Nouveau embroideries and textile: for instance in Amalija Matizena's works, made in the early 20th century.

Amalia Matisena. A towel with *chrysanthemums*. Beginning of 20th century¹⁹.

The Vase with *chrysanthemums*. China. End of 18th – beginning of 20th century. Is stored in the museum of Rundale palace²⁰.

Niklavs Strunke's *Fish Vase* is a striking example of Art Deco; however, it also refers to the Chinese traditional motif of fishes and the traditional scale and wave pattern. At the same time, the vase looks quite original and very Latvian, as the motif of fishes is also characteristic of Latvia.

¹⁸ Rundāle: Pils muzejs: Kolekcijas, 2001, Rundāle. Pils muzejs.

¹⁹ Rīgas Jugendstils. Katalogs. 2018.

²⁰ Rundāle: Pils muzejs: Kolekcijas, 2001, Rundāle. Pils muzejs.

Niklavs Strunke. *Fish vase*. 1930. Is stored in Latvian National Art museum²¹.

Vase with fish and dragon. China. 18th century. Is stored in Riga Bourse Art Museum²²

Speaking of Latvian chinoiserie products, Kuznetsov earthenware factory in Riga deserves a special mention. This factory was the Riga branch of the Kuznetsov factory, the largest Imperial Russian producer of porcelain, faience and majolica that exported its goods to Europe²³. The Riga branch of the Kuznetsov factory made copies of products developed by Russian craftsmen and created new products in collaboration with Latvian artists.

Dish with a lid. 1887-1915. Kuznecov's Factory, Latvian branch. It is stored in the Riga Art Nouveau Museum ²⁴.

Dish with a lid in the form of a fruit. China, 18th century. It is stored in St. Petersburg, in the State Hermitage ²⁵.

²¹ Valsts mākslas muzejs. Compl. by Māra Lāse. 2005.

²² Photo from the personal archive.

²³ Rīgas porcelāns un fajanss. 1984.

²⁴ Rīgas Jugendstils. Katalogs. 2018.

²⁵ Воображаемый восток: Китай «по-русски», XVIII – начало XX века (сост. О.А. Соснина), 2016.

A great contribution was made by modernist Roman Suta, who cooperated with the Kuznetsov factory but also worked in his own studio, Baltars. Many of his works include elements of chinoiserie and Japonism but they have their original look, bold and free and dissimilar to anything created before. To give an example, an Art Nouveau dish created by Suta based on his impressions from the performance of a Chinese theatre in Riga carries Chinese motifs but still looks very original.

Romans Suta. Chinese theatre in Latvia. Dish. 1926²⁶.

Chinese theatre. Illustration from the Chinese woodcut block from the R.Egle's and A.Upitis book "The history of world writing" (1930–1934). It is stored in the Andrejs Upitis Museum²⁷.

Suta also made famous sketches of Chinese costumes and scenography for the performance of the theatre plays *Iris* and *Turandot*.

R.Suta. Sketches to the P.Maskani's theatre play *Iris*. 1939²⁸

R.Suta. Sketches to the K.Gocci's theatre play *Turandot*, 1926²⁹

²⁶ <https://www.pinterest.com/pin/520236194432222959/>

²⁷ http://www.lnmm.lv/lv/apmekle/notikumu_kalendars/6625-muzejiska-akcija-celojums-austrumu-cels

²⁸ <http://www.lnmm.lv/lv/apmekle/pasakumi/6212-modernisma-laboratorija-kad-stabules-skanas-mirdz-kiniesu-dzejas-vakars-veltits-makslinieka-voldemara-matveja-140-dzimsanas-dienai>

Exhibitions as a means of influence

When examining the influence of Chinese art and chinoiserie on Latvia, it is important to trace not only the activities of single people and the fate of Oriental curiosities they brought with them but also exhibitions that showed this art to the mass audience. It is not improbable that Latvian artists were to some extent influenced by what they saw at such exhibitions.

Let us take a look at some exhibitions on China-related topics that took place in Latvia over the recent decades. Traditionally, most exhibitions were organized by the Latvian Museum of Foreign Art (today Riga Bourse Art Museum), but some took place in the Nature Museum, Riga Gallery, Latvian National Library, Riga Central Library and other venues. First public exhibitions of the Museum of Foreign Art date from 1869 but back then it did not have many Oriental items. Gradually, exhibitions of Oriental art gained momentum and collections increased their size. Besides exhibiting local collections, museums and galleries began to host exhibitions from China. An exhibition of 200 items of decorative art was brought from China in 1995³⁰. Two years later, an exhibition of fans and calligraphy took place, followed by an exhibition of Chinese prints in 1998, traditional Chinese ink paintings by Zhang Cuiying several years later, Chinese patterns in 2004, Chinese money in 2009, traditional Chinese batik in 2010³¹, numerous exhibitions of China and European porcelain, an exhibition of book illustrations and calligraphy in 2015, and the immense 2016-2017 exhibition *Silk Road. Ancient Chinese Art*³² that featured some 100 ancient Chinese artefacts and showed the public how the Eastern and the Western cultures interacted since the old times (3rd to 17th century AD).

In January 2017, the Latvian public had an opportunity to see Chinese and Japanese objects and works of art preserved in the personal museums of Latvian writers (Aleksandrs Caks, Andrejs Upits) and artists (Romans Suta and Aleksandra Belcova)³³.

The most grandiose event took place in 2019: Latvia, represented by the Riga Bourse Art Museum and the National History Museum of Latvia, took part in a large-scale project, the exhibition *Jewels of National Museums. The Heritage of the Silk Road* that took place in the National Museum of China in Beijing³⁴. Latvia was the only Baltic country present, along with twelve more countries of the world (Russia, Mongolia, Kazakhstan, Tajikistan, Romania, Slovenia, Poland, Oman, Cambodia, Japan, Korea). It showed 18 unique items from its collections. When selecting items for the exhibition, the Latvian Museum preferred those that highlighted the antiquity of cultural interchange between the two countries (the items covered the period between the 9th and the 19th centuries) and the history of trade relations on the Silk Road, or

²⁹ <https://www.fashionmuseumriga.lv/kaleidoscope/suta/>

³⁰ <https://www.vestnesis.lv/ta/id/27798>

³¹ <http://www.studija.lv/index.php?parent=2682>

³² <http://www.mumspatik.lv/zida-cels-senas-kinas-maksla/>

³³ http://www.lnmm.lv/lv/apmekle/notikumu_kalendars/6625-muzejiska-akcija-celojums-austrumu-cels

³⁴ <http://www.lnmm.lv/lv/mmr/b/apmekle/izstades/6587-izstade-pekina-p-zida-cela-mantojums-dargumi-nacionalajiem-muzejiem>

those that emphasized the influence of Chinese culture on Western European art. Simultaneously with the opening of the exhibition, the National Museum of China hosted the Global Forum of Museum Directors, inviting directors of national museums from 40 countries and 45 directors of China's largest museums. At this event, Latvia was represented by Daiga Upeniece, head of the Riga Museum of Art. The Forum made Latvia and Latvian national museums better known worldwide, giving them a better reach to their colleagues worldwide.

Activities of single individuals and artists

Chinese objects and stories of China also came to Latvia because of activities and travels to the East of many famous Latvian figures, such as Nikolaus von Himsel, a doctor, a collector, and an art sponsor; Peter Schmidt, linguist and ethnographer; Emil Bretschneider, physician and botanist; Viktors Seils, cartographer and traveller; Alexandra Gramolina, a Shanghai fashion star; Oscar Strock, a composer; Rihards Rudzītis, writer, translator and philosopher; and artists: Voldemars Matvejs, Nicholas Roerich, Aleksandra Belcova, Romans Suta, and Janis Plase, Julijs Straume. Nicholas Roerich made a great personal contribution in the 1920s – 1930s: he donated 45 of his works to the museum, and several more Roerich's paintings were donated by the Roerich Society in 1937. His famous paintings convey the spirit of the Chinese, Indian and Mongolian nature, of Tibetan mountains and Buddhist philosophy. They greatly influenced Roerich's contemporaries, attracted many admirers over the 20th century and stay topical today.

Nicolaus Roerich. On the high point (Tumo). 1936 ³⁵.

Art Nouveau and Art Deco were strongly influenced by Chinese and Japanese art. It is no coincidence that we mention Japanese art as it literally grew out of Chinese art³⁶. Japanese art

³⁵ <http://www.lnmm.lv/ru/mmr/b/poseti/vistavki/2587-nikolai-rierikh-i-latviia>

³⁶ Japanese art: Buddhist and Chinese Influences. 2012.

was very popular in the late 19th and early 20th century: its popularity started in 1867³⁷, after the Exposition Universelle in Paris when Japanese stamps and other art objects started to flow to Europe. It is a well-known fact that Vincent van Gogh, Claude Monet, Auguste Renoir and other Impressionists were much influenced by Japanese art (Japanism³⁸).

Latvia was also affected by this passion. Janis Rozentals's famous painting *Princess and Monkey* was probably in part influenced by *The Performing Monkey*, a Suzuki Harunobu's woodblock print, fabrics and jewelry and the vertical format include several elements of chinoiserie.

Janis Rozentals. *Princess with a Monkey*. 1913. Is located in Latvian National Museum of Art³⁹.

Suzuki Harunobu *The Performing Monkey*. 1760.⁴⁰

The influence of chinoiserie and Japanism is evident in the works of several artists of the early 20th century such as Julijs Straume (Art Nouveau drawings with floral motifs), Karlis Brencens (the composition of *The Woman*, 1904-1907), Julijs Feders (*Landscape with a Duck*), in graphic works of Sigizmunds Vidbergs (*In the Morning*, *Pearls* etc.) who was in love with Hokusai prints, in the works of Julijs Madernieks (*Autumn*, 1929), in the Vilhelms Purvītis's landscape *Spring. In Flower* (1933-1934), in Peteris Kalve's *Willows at the Edge of the Road* (1907) and his other works, in Peteris Upiťis's *Preparing the Wood*, in Eduards Brencens's *In the Boat* (1922), in works by Rihards Zariņš, Niklavs Strunke, Jazeps Kazaks, in Tatjana Rozenselda-Paulina's paintings and in Rudolfs Perle's watercolours and graphic works.

³⁷ Ю.Никитин. Всемирная выставка 1867 года в парижe. 2017. <http://www.mirvstavok.ru/2017-12-01/3358-vsemirnaja-vystavka-1867-goda-v-parizhe-napoleonovskie-plany-i-olim-pijskij-razmah.html>

³⁸ А.Арсеньева. Влияние Японии на европейских художников. 2019. <https://annaevart.ru/japan/>

³⁹ Edvarda Šmite. Princese ar pērtiķi. 2016. <http://www.studija.lv/?parent=7959>

⁴⁰ Emiko Ohnuki-Tierney. *The Monkey as Mirror: Symbolic Transformations in Japanese History and Ritual*. 1987.

Peteris Upits. Preparing wood. 1920ies ⁴¹

Sigismunds Vidbergs. Exlibris with Buddha ⁴²

Tatjana Rozenselda-Paulina «My birds bloom» 1935 ⁴³

Throughout the 20th century, Latvian artists were moderately interested in China. The examples that deserve mention are Sigurds Vidzirkste (*Without Name*, 1950, reminiscent of the Japanese Ensō circle), Eduards Kalnins (he visited China and made paintings of Chinese villages), Tatjana Rozenselda-Pauliņa (*My Birds in Bloom*, 1935, with images of cranes and swallows), Ojars Abols (abstract *Composition* with red and golden details, 1970s), Karlis Sunins and Felicita Pauluka. Since the 1990s, with the advent of the Latvian independence, Chinese topics became relevant once again, which is most likely due to the new possibilities of high-speed travel and trade, the emergence of means of rapid communication, and mass use of television and the Internet. Today, in the early 21st century, the interest for China continues to grow.

Eduards Kalnins. China studio. 1950ies⁴⁴

Marija Induse-Muceniece. Figutives boat. 1948⁴⁵

Karlis Sunins. The book "Fairy-tales about flowers" cover, 1966.⁴⁶

⁴¹ Valsts mākslas muzejs. Compl. by Māra Lāse. 2005.

⁴² O.Liepiņš. Sigismunds Vidbergs. 1942

⁴³ Valsts mākslas muzejs. Compl. by Māra Lāse. 2005.

⁴⁴ <http://www.antonija.lv/lv/izsole/43/lote-16-eduards-kalnins-1904-1988>

⁴⁵ <https://www.talsumuzejs.lv/ceturksna-prieksmets-marijas-induses-mucenieces-grafikas-darbs-beglu-laiva/>

Many Latvians visited China at the end of the 20th and the beginning of the 21st century, including a large number of artists, university students of art and other members of the artistic community, strengthening the connection between China and the Latvian art and making China closer and more understandable to the mass audience. Among those who contributed to these developments, it is important to mention such citizens of Latvia as Pyotr Aven, a porcelain collector; Aija Brivniece, a restorer of Chinese scrolls; Alexander Vasiliev, a historian of fashion; Ksenija Rudzīte and Natalija Sjunšalijeva, art historians; Pēteris Pildegovics and Agita Baltgalve, sinologists; and such Chinese artists as Mary Hunge Zhang (Riga), Chuang Xi and Zhao Yan (Bauska)⁴⁷.

Many Latvian artists of the late 20th and the early 21st century were, to a greater or lesser extent, influenced by Chinese or Japanese art. These are Aleksandrs Junkers, Naftolijs Gutmanis, Peteris Upitis, Rihards Skrubis, Iosifs Elgurts, Jazeps Delves, Arturs Duburs, Zelma Talberga, Aleksejs Naumovs, Lolita Zikmane, Kristaps Gelzis, Ilmars Blumbergs, Ivars Henrihsons, Vija Zarina, Guntars Sietins, Elina Alka, Dace Liela, Andris Eglītis, Vija Celmiņa, Rūta Opmane, Maija Dragune, Ilze Libiete, Anita Nikulceva, Daina Vignere, Silva Linarte, Janis Murovskis, Ilgvars Zalans.

Andris Eglītis. From the Earthworks cycle. 2011⁴⁸

Ilgvars Zalāns. Drawings on the rise paper with ink. 2010ies⁴⁹

Ilze Libiete. The high song. 1999⁵⁰

The works of these artists can be interpreted as being under the influence of Chinese composition, aesthetics, symbolism, philosophy, and calligraphy. Of course, all these similarities mentioned in this paper may be dismissed as coincidences, especially as only a few artists admit

⁴⁶ https://www.zvaigzne.lv/lv/gramatas/apraksts/104732-pasakas_par_ziediem_ar_k_sunina_ilustracijam.html?login_error=1

⁴⁷ <https://www.lsm.lv/raksts/dzive--stils/cilvekstasti/bauska-dzivojosi-kiniesu-makslinieki-iedvesmu-gleznam-gust-latvijas-daba.a320509/>

⁴⁸ Valsts mākslas muzejs. Compl. by Māra Lāse. 2005.

⁴⁹ <https://www.facebook.com/pegazsgalerija/photos/ilgvars-zal%C4%81ns-z%C4%ABm%C4%93jumi-artu%C5%A1u-uz-r%C4%ABspap%C4%ABra/1305846476195873/>

⁵⁰ From the personal archive

to having deliberately used the elements of Orientalism in their works. However, having examined the contact points of Chinese and Latvian art in their historical and contemporary context, we should be very naïve to presume that all the Chinese or Oriental reminiscences in the works of other artists are a pure coincidence. Indeed, these artists were directly or indirectly influenced by a great quantity of visual information somehow related to Chinese aesthetics and the Chinese culture in general.

Conclusion

This article has shown that despite the distance that separates China from Latvia, several types of contact points exist between the art of the two countries:

- import of Chinese art objects and works directly into Latvia or through Europe;
- import of the European chinoiserie;
- creation of authentic Latvian chinoiserie;
- influence of original Chinese art and chinoiserie on the Latvian art of various historical periods;
- influence of museum and private collections of Chinese art and chinoiserie on the image of Chinese art in Latvia;
- influence of Chinese and Latvian figures representing different spheres on the promotion of Chinese culture in Latvia;
- active cultural interaction of Latvia and China in various forms of political, exhibition, social, cultural and scholarly activities.

This article showed that in recent decades the relevance and interest of the topic have increased. Besides that, Latvian art and museum activities are reaching a new level and are becoming visible in China itself. This article was mainly dedicated to the influence of Chinese art on Latvia, as there are not many facts about the reverse influence, but this aspect can be studied in the future. The topic of this article is innovative and has so far been almost absent in research. There is also a need for a deeper study and analysis of Chinese art objects preserved in the repositories of Riga Bourse Art Museum, as only a few dozen out of approximately 500 items have been described in sufficient detail. It is especially important to fill in the gaps in the analysis of works of art that do not belong to the field of applied art such as scrolls of paintings and calligraphy, prints and other genres. In the future, there is also a need to study more thoroughly the works of Latvian artists that show the visible influence of Chinese and Japanese art, as well as the specific aspects of this influence – principles, themes, compositions and others. Given the importance of this topic, we believe that this study will fill in some of the gaps and establish a basis for further research. We believe that this work and its future continuation will make a significant contribution to the history of Latvian art.

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